

Base Adducts of N,N'-Di(thiocarbamoyl) Hydrazinato Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)

K. C. SATPATHY, T. D. MAHANA, R. K. PATEL and S. C. BEDBAK

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar, Burla (Sambalpur), Orissa

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Base adducts of the types, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DTU})\text{B}_2]$ and $[\text{M}(\text{DTU})\text{B}]$ [where $\text{M}=\text{Co}^{++}$ and Ni^{++} , $\text{H}_2\text{DTU}=\text{N,N}'\text{-di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine}$ and $\text{B}=\text{pyridine, picolines and quinoline}$] have been prepared and characterised. Basing on the spectral data and magnetic moment values, octahedral geometry has been proposed.

METAL complexes of N,N'-di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine (H_2DTU) with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II) and Mn(II) have been reported by us earlier¹. The complexes are highly insoluble in water and common organic solvents but they go into solution in nitrogen donor bases, such as pyridine, picolines and quinoline. The solubility in nitrogen donor bases may be due to the formation of base adducts. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterization of a few base adducts of N,N'-di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazinato metal(II) complexes and nitrogen donor bases.

Experimental

Methods and materials :

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes with N,N'-di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine were prepared by the method reported earlier¹.

Weighed quantities of N,N'-di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazinato metal(II) complexes and the bases were taken in two molar ratios 1:1 and 1:2. In the former ratio Ni(II) and Co(II) and in the latter ratio Cu(II) complexes were obtained. Attempts to synthesize Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes at higher ratio (1:2), however, failed. The appropriate metal complex and the base in the respective ratio was refluxed for 30 minutes when all the complexes were dissolved. It was filtered and the filtrate was allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature. The residue left after evaporation of the solvent was washed thoroughly with ethanol till free from any unreacted base and dried in vacuum and analysed.

The metal content of the complexes were determined according to standard procedures². Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate³. The carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents were determined by semimicro combustion process. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Physical measurements :

Infrared spectra of the ligand and the metal complexes were recorded in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer model 221 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurement was carried out at room temperature by Gouy method. Mercury(II) tetrathio-cyanato cobaltate(II), $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$, was used as a standard and diamagnetic corrections were made using standard values⁴. Electronic spectra of the complexes were taken by dissolving the samples in acetone.

Results and Discussion

The adducts are highly insoluble in water and alcohol but sparingly soluble in acetone. In the case of copper, the complexes obtained are of the composition, $\text{Cu}(\text{DTU})\text{B}_2$ ($\text{B}=\text{nitrogen donor base}$) but this loses a base molecule(B) on heating at 110-120°. The complexes of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) are quite stable at room temperature but decomposes above 120°.

Infrared spectra of the complexes have been studied with a view to confirm the coordination of the bases with the metal ions. The structurally important ir bands of the original metal complexes and the adducts are recorded in Tables 2-4. The spectral bands observed for the original metal complexes in the region 3400-3000 cm^{-1} , 1600 cm^{-1} , 1300 cm^{-1} , 1100 cm^{-1} and 750 cm^{-1} attributed to N-H stretching, C-N stretching, C-S stretching, NH_2 rocking, N-C-N stretching vibrations respectively, still persist in the series of adducts with minor variations in their respective band positions. In addition, it is remarkable to observe that two groups of bands appear in the region 1600-1440 cm^{-1} and 1380-1040 cm^{-1} respectively. The former series of bands arise due to ring vibrations of pyridine and quinoline and the latter series arise due to C-H in plane deformation vibrations. Usually four vibrational bands appear in the region 1600-1450 cm^{-1} for pyridines and picolines. It seems the highest frequency band which usually appears in the vicinity

TABLE-1 ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE BASE ADDUCTS OF N,N'-DI(THIOCARBAMOYL) HYDRAZINATO COPPER(II), NICKEL(II) AND COBALT(II)

Name of the adducts	Colour	μ_{eff} in B.M.	Metal %		Sulphur %		Nitrogen %		Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Cu(DTU)(Py) ₂	Chocolate	1.89	17.20	17.10	17.03	17.32	22.51	22.74	38.2	38.9	3.15	3.70
Cu(DTU)(α -pic) ₂	Grey	2.06	15.75	15.09	15.87	16.09	17.56	17.60	41.80	42.20	3.85	4.52
Cu(DTU)(β -pic) ₂	Grey	2.07	15.3	15.09	15.96	16.09	16.82	17.60	—	—	—	—
Cu(DTU)(γ -pic) ₂	Grey	2.15	15.5	15	15.85	16.09	18.98	17.60	40.4	42.2	3.9	4.52
Cu(DTU)(Q) ₂	Bluish black	1.89	13.41	13.53	13.26	13.62	17.75	17.88	50.9	51.11	3.43	3.83
Ni(DTU)(Py)	Olive green	2.80	20.65	20.53	23.23	22.40	23.83	24.56	—	—	—	—
Ni(DTU)(α -pic)	Grey	2.85	18.81	19.53	22.57	21.34	22.86	23.33	—	—	—	—
Ni(DTU)(β -pic)	Grey	3.30	18.92	19.53	20.54	21.34	22.87	23.33	—	—	—	—
Ni(DTU)(γ -pic)	Deep Grey	2.90	19.18	19.53	20.61	21.34	22.57	23.33	—	—	—	—
Ni(DTU)(Q)	Green	2.70	16.86	17.49	18.75	19.51	20.53	20.89	—	—	—	—
Co(DTU)(Py)	Grey	3.75	16.89	16.14	23.37	22.38	23.98	24.57	—	—	—	—
Co(DTU)(α -pic)	Brown	3.60	20.42	19.63	22.87	21.33	22.59	23.33	—	—	—	—
Co(DTU)(β -pic)	Brown	3.81	19.26	19.63	20.61	21.33	22.76	23.33	—	—	—	—
Co(DTU)(γ -pic)	Grey	3.62	20.61	19.63	20.74	21.33	22.89	23.30	—	—	—	—
Co(DTU)(Q)	Brown	3.78	16.44	17.55	19.05	20.14	20.64	20.84	—	—	—	—

 TABLE-2 INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF N,N'-DI(THIOCARBAMOYL) HYDRAZINATO COPPER(II) COMPLEXES AND ITS BASE ADDUCTS IN CM⁻¹

Cu(DTU)	Cu(DTU)(Py) ₂	Cu(DTU)(α -pic) ₂	Cu(DTU)(β -pic) ₂	Cu(DTU)(γ -pic) ₂	Cu(DTU)(Q) ₂	Assignments
3470 s	3460 s	3458 s	3480 s	3470 s	—	ν sym (NH ₂)
3450 s	—	3330 s	3220 s	3330 s	3330 s	ν asym (NH ₂)
1605 s	1605 s	1605 s	1608 s	1605 s	1600 m	ν (C...N) and ring vibrations
	1580 sh	1575 w	1580 m	1570 m	1570 sh	} Ring vibrations
	1515 s	1515 s	1515 s	—	1490 m	
	1455 m	1450 m	1450 m	1450 m	1450 m	
1300 s	1310 m	1308 s	1308 s	1305 m	1300 m	ν (C...S)
1300 s	1380 w	1385 w	1385 m	1380 w	1375 m	} CH in plane deformations
	1125 s	1125 s	1130 s	1122 s	1130 m	
	1050 w	1040 w	1045 w	1053 sh	1045 m, bd	
1100 s	1100 m	1100 m	1105 w	1105 m	1100 m	$\delta\gamma$ (NH ₂)
		910 w	900 vw	930 w	—	δ (CH ₂)
				840 w		
750 s	760 m, bd	—	760 m, bd	945 w	760 m	ν (C-S) + ν (C-N)

TABLE—3 INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF N,N'-DI (THIOCARBAMOYL) HYDRAZINATO COBALT(II) COMPLEXES AND ITS BASE ADDUCTS IN CM⁻¹

Co(DTU)	Co(DTU)(py)	Co(DTU)(α -ipc)	Co(DTU)(β -pic)	Co(DTU)(γ -pic)	Co(DTU)(Q)	Assignments
3420 s, bd	3500 m, bd	3400 m, bd	3420 m, bd	3420 m, bd	3440 m	ν sym (NH ₂)
3260 s, bd	3000 s	3000 s	3000 s	3000 s	3020 s	ν sym (NH ₂)
1605 s	1600 s	1610 m, bd	1610 m	1610 m	1600 m	ν (C—N) and ring vibrations
1515 s	1580 m	1580 m	1580 m	1580 m	1580 s	} Ring vibrations
	1475 s	1475 s	1475 s	1480 s	1460 s	
	1450 s	1450 m	1450 m	1445 m	1450 s	
1305 s	1300 s	1300 m	1300 m	1300 m	1300 s	ν (C—S)
	1380 s	1380 s	1380 s	1380 m	1380 s	} C-H in plane deformations
		1120 m	1140 m	1135 m	1140 m	
1100 s	1080 s, bd	1080 m				
	1100 m	1105 m	1105 m	1105 m	1100 m	$\delta\gamma$ (NH ₂)
		890 w	900 w	900 w		δ (CH ₂)
825 vw						
745 s	760 m	755 m	750 m	750 m	745 m	ν (C—S) + ν (C—N)

TABLE—4 INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF N,N'-DI (THIOCARBAMOYL) HYDRAZINATO NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES AND ITS BASE ADDUCTS IN CM⁻¹

Ni(DTU)	Ni(DTU)(py)	Ni(DTU)(α -pic)	Ni(DTU)(β -pic)	Ni(DTU)(γ -pic)	Ni(DTU)(Q)	Assignments
3480 s	3480 s	3480 s	348 m, bd	3460 s	3460 m	ν sym (NH ₂)
3360 s	3360 m, bd	3360 s	3360 s	3350 s	3360 s	
3340 w	—	—	—	—	—	
3200 w	3200 m, bd	3180 s	3180 s	3180 s	3200 m, bd	ν asy (NH ₂)
1605 s	1610 s	1608 s	1612 s	1610 s	1600 s	ν (C—N) and ring vibration
	1575 sh	1580 m	1590 m	1590 m	1580 s	} Ring vibrations
	1500 s	1480 s	1480 s	1480 s	1500 sh	
	1450 s	1450 s	1450 s	1455 s	1450 s	
1315 s	1300 m	1305 s	1300 s	1300 s	1300 s	ν (C—S)
	1380 s	1380 s	1380 s	1380 s	1380 s	} C-H in plane deformations
	1140 w	1120 w	1120 w	1120 w	1120 w	
	1040 w	1030 w	1040 w	1040 w	1060 m	
1150 s	1100 s	1100 m	1100 m	1100 m	1100 w	$\delta\gamma$ (NH ₂)
		900 w	900 w	900 w	930 w	} δ (CH ₂)
				840 w		
745 s	740 m	740 m	740 m	740 m	745 m	ν (C—S) + ν (C—N)

of 1600 cm^{-1} is overlapped by the C—N stretching band of the complexes. The vibrational bands of pyridines, picolines and quinoline and their metal complexes of the present study were also compared with the spectral data of Malik and coworkers⁵ which clearly manifest the shifting of C-H in plane deformation vibration to a higher frequency region. These results unambiguously suggest the coordination of nitrogen bases to the metal ion.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties :

The base adducts of N,N'-di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazinato copper(II) complexes possess magnetic moments in the range, 1.80-2.10 B.M. The electronic spectra show broad bands at $14,500$ and $23,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The former band arises due to d-d transition and the latter one is due to metal ligand charge transfer.

The electronic spectra of all the N,N'-di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazinato nickel(II) base adducts can be explained in a similar way. They show two bands at $13,800$ and $27,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The band at $13,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributed to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ transition for an octahedral geometry and the band at $27,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition. Magnetic moment of these adducts lie in the range 2.70-2.90 B.M.

The adducts of cobalt(II) complexes show a broad symmetrical band $\sim 16,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, characteristic of known octahedral complexes. This can be assigned to ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(P)$ transition in an approximately octahedral field. All the complexes are paramagnetic. The magnetic moments lie in the range 3.2-3.81 B.M. which is on the lower side of the expected magnetic moments of cobalt(II) octahedral complexes. Similar types of low magnetic moments have also been reported by Nandi and Ghosh⁶ but, however, no definite explanation has been given.

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